

2:BRF

2nd Balkan Rhino-Forum Sinusitis, Skull Base & Rhinoplasty Symposium

in conjunction with 4th Symposium of
Rhinology & Allergy Association of Serbia [RAAS]

Belgrade, Serbia, hotel Metropol Palace
04-06 APRIL 2019

PROGRAM and ABSTRACT eBOOK

Organizing Committee

Aleksandar Perić, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical Academy Faculty of
Medicine, University of Defence, Belgrade, Serbia,
President of Rhinology & Allergy Association of Serbia –
President of Organizing and Scientific Committee

Ljiljana Jovančević, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for
Diseases of Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of
Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia, Secretary of Rhinology &
Allergy Association of Serbia

Rajko Jović, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for Diseases of
Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Novi
Sad, Serbia, President of ENT Section of the Serbian
Medical Society

Aleksandra Barać, MD, PhD,
Scientific Associate, Clinical Center of Serbia, School of
Medicine, Belgrade, Serbia, Honorary Professor, University
of Sassari, Italy

Jelena Sotirović, MD, PhD,
Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical
Academy Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence,
Belgrade, Serbia

Uglješa Grgurević, MD,
Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical
Academy Faculty of Medicine, University of Defence,
Belgrade, Serbia

International Scientific Committee

Wytske Fokkens, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Academic Medical Center,
Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Sarah K. Wise, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Emory University,
Atlanta, USA

Nicolas Busaba, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Harvard Medical School
and Massachusetts Eye and Ear, Boston, USA

John DelGaudio, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Emory University,
Atlanta, USA

Sergei Karpischenko, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, First Pavlov Saint
Petersburg State Medical University, Saint Petersburg,
Russia

Jannis Constantinidis, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Aristotle University,
Thessaloniki, Greece

Christos Georgalas, MD, PhD,
Professor of Surgery/Head and Neck, University of
Nicosia/Program of St. Georges Medical School, Director of
Endoscopic Skull Base Hygeia Hospital, Athens, Greece

Gabriela Kopacheva Barsova, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, ENT -
University Hospital, University Campus "St. Mother
Theresa" Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia

Marc Scheithauer, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Head and Neck Surgery University
Hospital of Ulm, Ulm, Germany

Rajko Jović, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for Diseases of
Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Medical
Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

Livije Kalogjera, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, School of Medicine in
Zagreb, University Hospital „Sestre Milosrdnice“, Zagreb,
Croatia

Tomislav Baudoin, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, School of Medicine in
Zagreb, University Hospital „Sestre Milosrdnice“, Zagreb,
Croatia

Dilyana Vicheva, MD, PhD,
Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Medical University of
Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Aleksandar Perić, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Department of
Otorhinolaryngology, Military Medical Academy Faculty of
Medicine, University of Defence, Belgrade, Serbia

EUROPEAN RHINOLOGIC
SOCIETY

RHINOLOGY & ALLERGY
ASSOCIATION OF SERBIA

SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY

2:BRF

2nd Balkan Rhino-Forum
Sinusitis, Skull Base & Rhinoplasty Symposium

in conjunction with 4th Symposium of
RhinoLOGY & Allergy Association of Serbia [RAAS]

04-06 April 2019 • Hotel Metropol Palace, Belgrade, Serbia

Ljiljana Jovančević, MD, PhD,
Assistant Professor of Otorhinolaryngology, Clinic for
Diseases of Ear, Nose and Throat, Clinical Center of
Vojvodina, Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Novi
Sad, Serbia

Aleksandra Barać, MD, PhD,
Scientific Associate, Clinical Center of Serbia, School of
Medicine, Belgrade, Serbia, Honorary Professor, University
of Sassari, Italy

Technical organizer:

MedApp • e-mail: brfbelgrade@gmail.com • Phone: +381 64 5281 658

PHARMACEUTICAL EXCIPIENTS ASSOCIATED WITH NASAL PREPARATIONS SIDE EFFECTS

Nemanja Todorović¹, Tamara Tešić^{2,3}, Ljiljana Jovančević^{2,3}, Svetlana Goločorbin-Kon¹, Nebojša Pavlović¹, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

²Clinical Centre of Vojvodina, Clinic for Ear, Nose and Throat Diseases, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Background: Generally pharmaceutical excipients are pharmacologically inactive medicine constituents. However, there are many effects that some of them can cause. The aim of this study was to determine the presence of excipients with known effects (EKE) in registered nasal preparations (ATC groups R01).

Methods: The data of excipients were taken from the online available Summary of Product Characteristics (SmPC), at the web-sites of national medicines agencies of Serbia, Croatia and Slovenia. Further consideration of excipients was done in accordance with the recommendations of European Medicines Agency.

Results: Fifty-three medicines from Serbia, 46 from Croatia and 38 from Slovenia were processed. The highest percentage of medicines with EKE was among Serbian medicines (75.47 %) and they had the highest average number of EKE per medicine (1.40). The percentage of medicines that did not have the mentioned (all) EKE in section two of SmPC was also the highest here (37.50 %). Among the Slovenian medicines, 68.42 % contained EKE with an average number of 1.38 per medicine. 15.38 % of these medicines did not emphasise the presence of EKE in section two of the SmPC. Croatian medicines had the lowest percentage of medicines with EKE (54.35 %), as well as the smallest average number of EKE per medicine (1.08). Only 12 % of medicines with EKE did not have their content mentioned in the section two of the SmPC. The most common EKE in all three countries was benzalkonium chloride, which can cause irritation and swelling of mucosa in nasal use.

Conclusions: National regulations are largely aligned with EU regulations, but they are not fully respected in terms of EKE labeling. The presence, characteristics and labeling of EKE in the analyzed medicines require additional caution when prescribing and issuing this group of medicines.